

PHRASEOLOGICAL UNITS WITH A COLOR NAMING COMPONENT AS A MEANS OF REFLECTING THE SELF-CONSCIOUSNESS OF THE ENGLISH PEOPLE

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Annotation: *In this article, it is explained the phrasal verb unit, which is part of the color name, through the expression of self-awareness and attitude in English. This article presents an analysis of the work of a famous British author and the equivalence of color combinations taken from original dictionaries and reference books. Readers will not only discover new phrases, but also learn the symbolic meaning of color and some features of the English language.*

Keywords: *phraseological unit; concept; colour perception; symbolism*

The relevance of this topic is due to the fact that the study of phraseological units is a necessary link in the process of mastering a foreign language, since their use eliminates the need to use additional words, makes speech more vivid and figurative, helps to understand the national culture of the country of the language being studied. It should be noted that the topic of the use of color in the language was previously raised in the works of such scientists as Krasnykh V.V. (Ethnopsycholinguistics and linguoculturology, 2001), Alimpieva R.V. (Color images as a means of expressing anthropocentricity in the literary texts of Adam Mickiewicz and, 2005), Vasilevich A.P. (Etymology of color names as a mirror of national and cultural consciousness, 2007), Vendina T.I. (Semantic-symbolic paradigm of color in the context of word formation, 2000) and Frumkina R. M. (Color, meaning, similarity, 1984). However, despite such a variety of works, this problem remains relevant for study, since many of its aspects are still not disclosed. There are over 15 thousand phraseological units in the English language, and there are special dictionaries for them, where phraseological units are classified by topic. The present work is devoted to one of the topics - phraseological units with color naming components. We analyzed some phraseological units with a pronounced color naming component. This group includes lexemes that contain the following concepts: black, blue, red, white, brown, green, gray, pink, purple, yellow. Let us consider the frequency of use of these phraseological units in English works of three completely different genres: in the novel *The Teacher* (1857) by Charlotte Brontë, in the detective story *The Sign of the Four* (1890) by Arthur Conan Doyle, and in the comedy "Three Men in a Boat, Not Counting the Dog" (1889).) writer

Jerome Klapka Jerome. We chose the listed works, since they were all created in the same period - during the transition of the romantic literary direction to the realistic one (19th century). All three works are classical and programmatic for learning English. The most important criterion for selecting works is their assignment to different genres, which helped us to make the most accurate conclusion about the frequency of use of "colored" expressions in English literature.

In the work of Arthur Conan Doyle "The Sign of Four" there are nine phraseological units with the concept of black. In the novel "Teacher" "black" phraseological units appear five times. In the comedy "Three in a boat, not counting the dog" there are only two phraseological units with a black designation. Black color symbolizes evil, grief and misfortune. Among the phraseological units with the black color element, the group denoting the negative emotional states of a person predominates. For example, in the detective story "The Sign of Four" we meet such phraseological units as: "fits of the blackest depression", "as black as thunder", in the comedy "Three in a Boat": "was black in the face". Black phraseological units describe the appearance of people, objects, for example, in the novel "Teacher": "raven-black hair", "flash in his black eye", or in the comedy "Three Men in a Boat": "the black gentleman". As for the red color, its interpretations are also diverse. In the detective story The Sign of Four, the concept red occurs four times, in the comedy Three Men in a Boat three times, and in the novel The Teacher there are two red expressions. These phraseological units denote feelings and emotions, for example, in the detective story "The Sign of Four": "roars himself red in the face", "it was a red light"; "Three in a boat": "he laughed until his ears were quite red" or the appearance of a person, as in the novel "Teacher": "her hair was red - quite red." The third place in the total number of color phraseological units is occupied by white. In Conan Doyle's detective story, there are seven PUs with a white component. There are two "white" expressions in Charlotte Brontë's work. In Jerome K. Jerome's comedy, there were no phraseological units with a white component. White color symbolizes not only purity and innocence, but also negative character traits, as in the detective story "The Sign of Four": "white feather in the side". The white color is also used in the meaning of "pale": "her face grew white to the lips", "she turned so white that I feared she was about to faint", "Morstan had turned deadly white" ("Sign of the Four"). As can be seen from the examples, white phraseological units can describe appearance or character: "Sign of four" - "a heap of white hair", "Teacher" - "I am no Oriental; white necks, carmine lips", "that made a perfect white demon of her". Gray is neutral. In "The Sign of Four" we find three "gray" examples. In the novel "The Teacher" - two. But in the comedy "Three Men in a Boat" there are no phraseological units with a gray component. More often, "gray" phraseological units denote old age, gray hair: - "overhung by long gray side-whiskers", "curly

hair was thickly shot with gray" ("Sign of the Four"), "the hair grown grey", "her gray hair strangely disheveled" ("Teacher"). In fifth place in terms of the number of uses is the blue concept. Blue has similar symbolic meanings to black. It was considered mourning in ancient Egypt and South Africa. In English, blue is most often associated with longing: "softened by a mild melancholy blue eye", "I saw it all blue" ("Teacher"). This color also symbolizes constancy and nobility. In the work of Jerome K. Jerome, the "blue" idiom is used once: "the "old blue" that we hang about our walls were common every day." In the detective story "The Sign of the Four", expressions with the blue concept do not occur. "Green" and "brown" expressions shared the sixth place in terms of frequency of use as part of color phraseological units. In ancient times, brown was given a negative meaning. It is considered a symbol of despondency and depression. Most often, this concept is used in phraseological units that describe the appearance of people or objects, such as in the work of Jerome K. Jerome: "to light a bit of brown paper", or in the description of a gloomy and dirty environment: "rain-drops falling on its brown and sluggish waters" or: "brown, heavy clouds were drifting across the sky" ("The Sign of the Four"). Green is associated with nature, freshness: "Three in a boat" "George suggested meat, tomatoes and green stuff." We find two "green" phraseological units in the work of Charlotte Bronte: "get a glimpse of the green region", "a lane as green as the lawn". Yellow means modesty, cowardice, an example of which we see in the novel "The Teacher": "Madame Pelet was meagre and yellow", and also describes objects and phenomena: "The Sign of the Four" "make after that launch with the yellow light". Purple is the color of royalty and supreme beauty. Only one phraseological unit with the concept of purple appears in the work of Charlotte Bronte: "I saw the purple light of love". Pink colour wasn't met in any mentioned work. This color symbolizes tenderness and lightness. Pink is present in a few English phraseological expressions, denoting a positive emotional state: (be in the pink, to be tickled pink) or speaking in the meaning of "top of perfection": (the pink of perfection). Thus, each color has a certain symbolism. As can be seen from our study, phraseological units are a kind of mirror that reflects the distinctive features and characteristics of a particular nation.

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